

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF NATURAL FIBRE STRUCTURES SUBJECTED TO BUCKLING LOADS

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ABSTRACT

In this study natural fibre sandwich structures, with and without implanted delamination were fabricated using the compression moulding technique. For both types of structures the face sheets were made from sisal (jet mat 550) set in an epoxy (LR-20) matrix with structural PVC core (herex C 70/75). The structures were subjected to loading in the in-plane direction. The out of plane deflection of both inner and outer skins were measured and were found to be marginally out of phase for the delaminated specimens. The global panel failure in each case was accompanied by subdued cracking sound mainly coming from the fracture of the face sheet.

MSC. Patran was successfully used to verify the experimental results. The numerical solution shows a 13 % reduction in the out of plane deflection. In addition microscopy and SEM analysis were also performed on the fractured specimens.

KEYWORDS: Natural Fibre, Delaminated Structures, Buckling

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials dates back centuries ago, and started with natural fibres, when clay was reinforced by straw to build walls. Later on, natural fibre lost much of its appeal, when other more durable construction materials such as metals were introduced. During the sixties, composite materials were reintroduced when glass fibres in combination with tough rigid resins could be produced on a large scale. Over the years these materials have been refined and are now preferred because of their high strength to weight ratios, easy mouldability and durability [1]. However the products of these materials are very costly to produce, therefore there has been a renewed interest in the field of natural fibre structures.

Potential advantages of weight saving, lower raw material price, and biodegradable properties have motivated researches to consider natural fibre as a substitute for glass fibres [1-3]. However, natural fibres have their shortcomings. These include a lower durability and strength when compared to glass fibres. Recent experimentation reveals that by pre-treating the fibres with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) significantly improves the fibre-matrix adhesion and hence increases the strength of the product [4-6]. These pre-treated fibres satisfy the requirements for low-end applications such as interiors of motor vehicles and low cost housing. In further developments, Schledjewski R. [7] enhanced mechanical properties of natural fibre pre-preg structures by increasing the mould pressure.

In considering these developments structures may fail in a variety of ways. One of the modes of failure is buckling. When a slender structural member is subjected to compressive loading,

it will bend and deflect in the out of plane direction. After a substantial out of plane deflection the member is said to have buckled. Many researches have analysed the effects of buckling with and without delaminations and have developed different models for each case.

One of the first people to develop working model was Babcock C.D. [8]. This model was fairly accurate in predicting the behaviour of the beam, but was limited, since it was a one dimensional model. Later on Sallam S. [9], including [10-13], studied the buckling analysis of single delaminated structures considering various different effects. They first developed an analytical model based on buckling and classical fracture mechanics. Their results showed a decrease in load with an increase in delamination size. These results were further verified via experimentation.

Kim and Dharan [14] developed a simplified mechanics of materials model and an extension of the Vizzini–Lagace delamination buckling model [15] to determine the local buckling behavior of a sandwich column containing two symmetrically located face-core delaminations. Propagation of the debond was predicted from the potential energy of the delaminated sandwich using linear, small deflection analysis, which unfortunately, is not expected to yield accurate results for such an inherently nonlinear problem [16].

Hong C.S. [17] studied the buckling and post-buckling analysis of single and multiple laminated orthotropic beams by nonlinear finite element analysis. He employed constraints at the overlap region in the load incremental procedure. Using this model of multiple delaminations, accurate results were obtained for buckling and post buckling behaviour of composite laminates.

In considering all the work conducted on conventional sandwich structures some researches decided to explore the differences between natural fibres and synthetic fibres. Wambua P. [18] has recently published a paper examining the properties several different natural fibres, one of which is sisal and compared the results with conventional glass fibres. Tests revealed that the natural fibres compared favourably with the corresponding properties of glass fibres and in some cases better than those of glass. In addition independent studies carried out by a leading automotive company, General Motors in association with other companies involved in bio-composites support Wambua's findings. Upon examination of all the above mentioned papers and findings it is evident that little is known about the specific behaviour of sisal sandwich structures under buckling conditions.

Previous research conducted revealed different mathematically methods to calculate the critical buckling load and hence verified by FEA. These methods are well suited for synthetic and certain natural fibre composite structures. They are also unable to determine point or time taken for buckling to occur under quasi-static loading. By knowing the point at which buckling occurs, early warning systems such as audio and visual devices can be implemented in order to avoid catastrophic failure.

In this study, sandwich structural members were constructed using natural fibre (sisal) with epoxy LR 20 resin and PVC foam core (Herex C70.75). Natural fibre and epoxy face sheets with no delamination were manufactured. During the manufacturing process of composite structures insufficient resin infusion causes in-situ delamination. Further more, in industry tool drops could also cause localised delamination. Therefore panels with implanted delamination were also manufactured to determine the effect a delamination has on structural integrity. These specimens were subjected to axial loading to induce a buckling effect. The load, axial displacement, out of plane deflection and strain at the inner and outer face sheets

were recorded. In addition the FEM package MSC. Patran was used to verify the experimental results and light microscope combined with SEM analysis were also performed.

2. MANUFACTURING PROCESS

Composite structures with natural fibre (Sisal – Jetmat/S/0550 random fibre) face sheets were manufactured using a compression moulding technique. The fibres for the lower face sheet were placed onto the bottom mould surface and then wetted until the fibres were saturated with the resin. The foam core (Herex C70.75) was then placed over the lower face sheet and the upper face sheet above the foam. The upper face sheet was then wetted until it was saturated with resin. The composite lay up was then placed into a compression press to remove the excess resin. The panel was left in the press to cure, after which it was then removed and cut into test coupons (length 275 mm and width 25 mm). After the test coupons had been cut and polished (to remove surface imperfections) they were fitted with strain gauges (LY11-6/350A). Rough or jagged edges cause stress concentration and evidently lead to premature failure.

In addition to the above mentioned panel, panels with an implanted delamination were also manufactured using the same process. A strip of polyethylene measuring 50 mm in width was placed across the width of the panel (see figure 4 and figure 5 shaded area).

Figure 2: Top view of panel with shaded area being the Implanted Delamination

Figure 3: Side view showing different types of test coupons prepared

As can be seen from figure 2 the test coupons were cut across the delaminated area (cut along the dash lines). Figure 3 show the configuration of the different panels manufactured. The delamination breaks the bond between the face sheet and the core, thus prohibiting the transfer of load.

3. EXPERIMENTATION

Quasi-static buckling tests were performed on a minimum of four specimens of each type using a Lloyds Tensile Tester fitted with a 20 kN load cell. The cross-head speed was set at 1 mm/min. The experimental setup can be seen in figure 4. A dial gauge was used to measure the out of plane deflection of the outer face sheet. A second dial gauge was used to measure the relative movement of the inner face sheet. The test coupon was the clamped into the in-house designed test fixture detailed later. The load and in-plane deflection were obtained from the Lloyds tensile tester. The strain gauges (LY11-6/350A) were mounted on the inner and outer face sheets as shown in figure 3.

Figure 4: Typical setup of buckling test using a Lloyds Tensile Tester fitted with a 20 kN load cell, dial gauges and strain gauges.

The conventional test fixture do not allow for rotation of the beam. This causes localised stresses at the grips which cause premature failure of the specimen and show incorrect buckling load, shown in figure 5. Therefore an in-house test fixture was designed to allow one degree of freedom about the pivot point. The pivoting motion allows the specimen to deflect freely in the out of plane direction which significantly reduces the stresses induced at the grips. This is shown in figure 6.

Figure 5: Conventional grips, cause localised stress areas

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The buckling analysis in this investigation was conducted through a few sequential steps. First, the load-displacement behaviour was analysed in conjunction with the strain gauge data to determine the critical buckling load. Second, the influence of implanted delamination was studied by analysing the load-displacement data for the delaminated plates.

4.1 Buckling Tests Performed On Specimens without Delamination

The load-displacement behaviour for in and out of plane for specimens without implanted delamination is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Load vs. Deflection (in plane and out of plane) response for natural fibre sandwich beam without delamination

The initial ramp up region up to the failure point for all categories is similar. Because of the relatively high compressive modulus, the face sheets carried the major portion of the load compared to the core. A close observation of Figure 7 indicates that failure load is approximately 1900 N. The panel without delamination had the highest failure load, which is about 90% more than the failure load of the samples with delamination. After the initial buckling at 1900 N, there is a sharp drop in the load until 1200 N, and then fails almost catastrophically. This suggests the presence of a rapidly progressing failure mode during the final failure event. The global panel failure in each case was accompanied by subdued cracking sound mainly coming from the fracture of the face sheet.

The out of plane deflection of the tension face and compression face appear to be the same. This suggests no compaction of the core. The out of plane deflections were further investigated and the resulting comparison is shown in figure 8.

Figure 8: Stress vs. Strain response for natural fibre sandwich beam without delamination

The stresses shown in Figure 8 were computed from the load values in figure 7. The corresponding strain values were recorded directly off the strain gauge amplifier. In figure 8 both the inner and outer strains have the same profile. This is because the core acts as a

medium through which the direct stresses are transferred. The stress distribution in a composite beam is shown in the figure 9.

Figure 9: (a) Simply supported beam with transverse load, (b) Direct and shear stress distribution in a sandwich beam under three point bend test (Extract from *Mechanics of Materials* by Gere and Timoshenko)

As can be seen from the figure *the faces carry bending moments as tensile and compressive stresses and the core carry transverse forces as shear stresses* (Extract from *Mechanics of Materials* by Gere and Timoshenko). This behaviour is characteristic of a monolithic beam where the inner and outer strains are of the same magnitude but have different directions. The initial response of the beam shows that the strain at the face sheets gradually increase as the stress increases. After taking up a stress of 2 MPa, there is a 150% rise in stress but only 7% increase in strain. This is due to the load being absorbed by the core and induces shear stress within the core. The relationship between the outer and inner strains can be better compared if the strains are plotted against tensile and compressive stresses. This is shown in figure 10.

Figure 10: Tensile and Compressive Stresses vs. Strain response for natural fibre sandwich beam without delamination

Shown in figure 10, the strains from both (inner and outer) gauges are compressive up to certain time, and then they begin to diverge. After this time interval, one gauge continues to monitor compressive strain while the other begins to record tensile strain. This is a clear indication of the initiation of the buckling of the specimen.

After taking a stress of approximately 4.5 MPa, the outer face sheet experiences a sharp increase in stress with a marginal decrease in strain. The inner face on the other hand does not

experience this. Evidently the inner face sheet is strained more than the outer face sheet which is suggestive of core compaction. However, this compaction is very slight as there is no visible damage of the core in the fractured specimen. This is shown in figure 11.

Figure 11: Crack Propagation through a natural fibre test coupon without delamination

In terms of the loading, it is expected that failure would occur at the mid-point, since this area will experience the greatest buckling load. However, this did not occur. Failure took place in a region 40mm from the centre of the beam (axial direction). Failure was initiated by fibre cracking and hence followed by the formation shear crack approximately 45° to the vertical, from the tension face towards the compression face. Before reaching the centre of the beam the crack propagated away from the bond line at an angle of approximately 45° and at the centre moving down to the bond line at 45°. This suggests the maximum shear stress experienced at the centre of the beam. The specimens showed no signs of fibre wrinkling as when compared to synthetic fibres.

4.2 Buckling Tests Performed On Specimens with a Single Delamination

In the case of a single implanted delamination in the panel, the load-displacement behaviour changes slightly as seen in figure 12.

Figure 12: Load vs. Deflection (in plane and out of plane) response for natural fibre sandwich beam with a single delamination

The failure load is lower than what it was observed in figure 7. The post failure behaviour is quite different. Both demonstrate permanent deformation behaviour after the failure. These are characteristics of unstable deformation, and are due to the progression of the uncontrolled core-skin debonding. Experimental buckling loads for the delaminated panels, shown in figure 12, show a 90% reduction in buckling load due to the presence of Teflon. The profile of the load vs. displacement curves depicted this paper are in good agreement with Chattopadhyay [19] findings.

The in and out of plane deflections behave in a non-linear manner. This suggests a decrease in the ductility of the material emanating from the delamination. As seen before, after the critical load of 1050 N, the beam becomes unstable and starts deflecting rapidly without an increase in load.

The out of plane deflections apparently behave in a similar manner, as in the case without delamination. However, a closer examination, shown in figure 13, reveals this to be otherwise.

Figure 13: Stress vs. Strain response for natural fibre sandwich beam with a single delamination

Figure 13 shows that the inner strain curve has the same profile as the strain curves in figure 8. This is because there is no delamination at the inner face sheet. Hence the load is similarly transferred into the core, as in the first case. However, the outer strain curve has a very irregular profile. Initially there is a negative strain on the outer face sheet. This indicates compaction of the core. After taking up a stress of 1 MPa, the strain increases significantly as the stress increases. This suggests that there is no transfer of the load into the core from the outer face sheet. This can be clearly seen in figure 14, as there is no rupturing of the core immediately beneath the fractured face.

Figure 14: Crack Propagation through a natural fibre test coupon with a single delamination

Failure was initiated by the fracture of the outer face sheet at the centre. The crack then propagated along the delaminated portion in both directions. Upon reaching the end of the delaminated area, a mode one crack developed and travelled through the core on both sides until the bond line of the inner face sheet. It then developed into a mode two crack and travelled away from the delaminated portion and along the bond line in both directions.

4.3 Buckling Tests Performed On Specimens with Two Delaminations

In the case of a two sided delaminated panel, the load-displacement behaviour is significantly different from the above cases, as seen in figure 15.

Figure 15: Load vs. Deflection (in plane and out of plane) response for natural fibre sandwich beam with two delaminations

As seen before, in figure 12, the structure behaves in a similar manner. After taking a load of 1000 N, the in and out of plane deflections continue to increase in a non linear path with no decrease in the load and hence, since there is no bond between the core and face sheets, the load is not transferred. Therefore it is expected that stress-strain profile would be similar to the outer strain curve in figure 13. However, this is not the case, as shown in figure 16.

Figure 16: Stress vs. Absolute Strain response for natural fibre sandwich beam with two delaminations

The inner strain follows the same profile as in figures 8 and 13. Although there is a delamination on the compression face, the load is still being transferred to the core. The reason for this is that the compressive face pushes against the core, simulating a bond. After taking up a stress of 1.6 MPa, the outer face sheet follows the profile of figure 13. This

implies that no load is transferred to the core from the outer face sheet. Crack propagation occurred differently from the single delaminated test coupon. This is shown in figure 17.

Figure 17: Crack Propagation through a natural fibre test coupon with two delaminations

Failure occurred as expected that at the mid-point, since this area experienced the greatest buckling load. The failure was initiated by fibre cracking and hence, followed by the immediate formation of a shear crack through the core from the tension face to the compression face. Upon reaching the compression face the crack travelled along the delaminated area and the through the bond line in both directions.

When the results from figures 7, 12 and 15 are compared they show conformance with previous research conducted by Taheri F. [20] and Kim H. [21]. They experimented with load vs. varying delamination ratios.

5. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

FEM package MSC. Patran was successfully used for this analysis. Shell element with 21 nodes and a quad 4 mesh were used. Quadrilateral elements rather than triangular element mesh was selected, since they offered more accurate results -Geyer, S.E [22].

The left side of the beam was fixed (translation $x, y, z = 0$) but allowed to rotate about the z axis. On the right side translations y and z were fixed and a load was applied along the x axis in the negative direction. This model was further developed to incorporate a delamination between the core and face sheets.

Figure 18: 3D Model of natural fibre sandwich structure with end plates

In figure 18 the green area represents the natural fibre face sheets, blue area represents the pvc foam core and the red area represents two metal plates constructed from mild steel. For modelling purposes metal plates were introduced to avoid localised stress concentrations at the ends of the composite structure and to evenly distribute the load to the face sheets and core respectively. Once again, the above-mentioned boundary conditions were applied to the mid-point of each metal face.

For the specimens without delamination an equivalence test was performed to eliminate all coinciding nodes. This omitted any imperfection within the structure. The results obtained from the shell model and 3D model are in good correlation.

Figure 19: Placement of delaminations for samples with two delaminations

When performing the equivalence test for specimens with delaminations, the coinciding nodes, for the length of the delamination were ignored. Therefore creating an un-bonded surface between the face sheet and the core, thus simulating a delamination. The F.E.A geometry described above is in agreement with a paper by Hu N. [23]

The model was developed using a linear code and figure 20 shows marginal difference between the FEM and experimental results for all specimens up to the elastic limit. Thereafter the model does not take into account the plastic behaviour of the beam.

Figure 20: Load vs. Out of Deflection response for natural fibre sandwich beam with no delaminations

As can be seen from the stress plot the end plates absorb the point load and distribute it evenly throughout the cross section of the beam. The face sheets carry more of the tensile and compressive stresses than the core, this verifies the previous discussion. Since there are no debonds there is a transfer of stresses from the tensile face to the compressive face via the core.

Figure 21: Stress plot for samples without delamination

Figure 22 shows, at the ends, a load being transferred into the core that is because of the gripping mechanism. As the load approaches the centre of the beam it reaches it decreases to a minimum because of the debond between the core and face sheets. This is discussed in detail in section 4.2.

Figure 22: Stress plot for natural fibre sandwich beam with single delamination

6. SEM AND MICROSCOPY

The fractured specimens of the buckling tests were analysed using a Philips XL30 Environmental SEM with accelerating voltage 0.2 to 30 kV and magnification 15 to 500 000. The microscope is equipped with a conventional filament emission gun giving a beam spot size of 20 nm and image resolution of 2 nm. All specimens were analysed at three main areas. Namely face sheet fracture, core fracture and bond line fracture. Post examination of these three areas revealed similar results in each case.

Figure 23: Crack Propagation through a natural fibre test coupon without delamination

Figure 24: Face-core fractured surface at bond line

Figure 25: Face-core fractured surface at bond line (50x) under SEM

Figures 24 and 25 reveal a resin rich interface layer upon which fragments of the core are also noticeable indicating that the resin didn't propagate into the core. The crack therefore propagated along the edge of the soft core until reaching the mid point of the beam and then propagated into the core. This is due to the rapid growth of shear stresses within the core, discussed in section 4.1.

Figure 26: General fractured face for natural fibre specimens

Figure 27: Crack Propagation through a natural fibre test coupon with a single delamination

Fibre pullout

Figure 28: Fibre pullout for natural fibre specimens

At the fractured face, fibre pull-out as well as fractured fibres can be seen. Since the fibres have a random orientation the instantaneous crack propagation is not consistent, but falls within a given region. i.e. approximately 3mm above and below the crack initiation. Differences in each fibre seen in figure 27 i.e. diameter, strength, etc, also contribute to the slight deviation in the crack propagation.

General core failure was due to core compaction (collapse of cells). This reduced the ability of the core to maintain its rigidity and to efficiently transfer the loads. Figure 29 supports the discussion in sections 4.2 and 5.

Figure 29: Collapse of PVC Foam core

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this study quasi-static buckling tests were performed on natural fibre sandwich composites. Specimens without delamination, with single delamination and with two delaminations were prepared. The results were further verified using MSC. Patran
From the results obtained it is evident that:

- When the delamination was placed on the compression of the beam it has no effect on the buckling load carrying capacity.
- If the implanted delamination was placed on the tension side the beam, it behaved like a monolithic beam, in that the buckling loads increased and there was a reduction in shear loads. This resulted in the fracture of the beam and a reduction in the out of plane deflection.
- For beams having a delamination on the tension side as well as both sides the out of plane deflection was found to be marginally out of phase. This phase shift results in the buckling loads (bending) transitions into a shear load into the core.
- Beams with delaminations on both sides have a reduced ability to carry the buckling loads. In general these beams can only carry 60 % of the load before failure.
- A novel method was used to validate the time taken for buckling to occur. For the specimens test the buckling time ranges between 15 to 20 seconds.
- Commercially available MSC. Patran, finite element model, can successfully predict (within 13 %) the buckling behaviour of natural fibre structures.

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